

STABILITY OF ASYNCHRONOUS MULTIRATE LINEAR SYSTEMS

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Abstract

This paper develops a sufficient stability criterion for unsynchronized, multirate, sampled-data systems. Such hybrid systems include a linear, time-invariant plant and several unsynchronized digital controllers. The criterion, which is computed from eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the closed-loop state transition matrix, objectively describes long- and short-term stability. A simple example illustrates the method.

Introduction

Previous multirate analysis and design methods assumed synchronous sampling such that the system was periodic. Specifically, the composite sample sequence repeated exactly after some period. These methods generally fell into two classes: frequency domain methods and time domain methods. Sklansky's Frequency Decomposition [1] and Kranc's Switch Decomposition [2] were early frequency domain techniques. A general state space analysis technique, described by Kalman and Bertram [3], formed the basis for subsequent time-domain design methods. Several researchers [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], and [9] solved the optimal, full-state-feedback multirate regulator design problem. Berg addressed a more general problem, where the controller had a restricted form such as partial state feedback [10].

While theory addressed only synchronous systems, asynchronous sampled-data control schemes had practical real-world applications. Distributed, digital processors might reduce cost or improve reliability, particularly for a geographically distributed plant. Consequently, asynchronous digital design is a natural approach for some large or distributed systems. Simulations, while useful for evaluating system performance, do not assure stability under all synchronization conditions. Therefore, a new stability analysis method was needed. This paper develops a sufficient stability condition for the asynchronous case.

Scope

This paper extends multirate stability theory to evaluate asynchronous linear sampled-data systems. This type of system (see Figure 1) is a hybrid, composed of:

- a time-invariant, continuous-time part described by $\dot{x}_c = Ax_c + Bu$, where A and B are constant matrices, x_c is a continuous state vector, and $u = x_s$;
- sample-and-hold elements with outputs x_s described by transitions of the form $x_s(t^+) = S_s X(t^-)$, where each S_s is constant matrix, and $X = [x_c^T x_s^T x_d^T]^T$; and

- a digital (computer) part described by difference equations of the form $x_d(t^+) = D_d X(t^-)$, where each D_d is constant matrix.

This structure is quite general. The measurement and feed-forward matrices (C and D in the standard $\dot{x} = Ax + Bu$, $y = Cx + Du$ formulation) are embedded in the S_s and D_d matrices. All signals in Figure 1 represent vector quantities. In particular, there may be several different, independent sample-and-hold elements and digital state updates. The timing of these discrete-time state transitions (i.e., x_s and x_d updates) may be controlled by any finite number of periodic sample schedules with arbitrary periods.

Figure 1: Linear Sampled-Data Control System

The asynchronous stability criterion is suitable for synchronous or asynchronous multi-input/multi-output systems. The main restriction is that the system's closed loop state transition matrix must have a full set of eigenvectors for non-zero eigenvalues. The analysis approach uses synchronous sample patterns to approximate asynchronous patterns. Then, a synchronous analysis approach is used along with a safety factor sufficient to account for the difference between the actual sample pattern and the synchronous approximation. The resulting stability criterion is sufficient to guarantee asynchronous stability, but does not prove instability. The criterion also provides a figure of merit analogous to a rightmost s-plane bound for the poles of a linear, time-invariant continuous-time system. Necessary and sufficient conditions for asynchronous stability were not established.

The method extends to any finite number of periodic samplers with arbitrarily complex sample patterns. However, for brevity and clarity, this paper only addresses simple systems with two samplers. A detailed treatment of this method that also includes an optimal asynchronous design method and implementing PC-MATLAB computer code is presented in [11].

Fundamentals

Multirate systems have two or more independent digital controllers as shown in Figure 2. The relative timing between the sample processes will be called "phase". The overall sequence of events, or composite sample schedule, is found by superimposing events from the independent sampling processes as shown in Figures 3 or 4. The intuitive concept of asynchronous sampling (i.e., independent samplers with no master clock) is essentially correct. The rest of this section develops these concepts and terms with more rigor.

Figure 2: Simultaneous Independent Controllers

Definitions

Sequences, Events, and Segments: A *sequence* is any periodic schedule of discrete-time events. The top two sampler schedules in Figure 3 are periodic and represent sequences. The composite sample schedule in Figure 3 is a sequence because it, too, is periodic. The composite sample schedule in Figure 4 is not a sequence because it is aperiodic. Discrete-time state transitions, indicated by labeled vertical arrows in Figures 3 and 4, are called *events*. Intervals between the events in a composite schedule are *segments*. Discrete-time states are constant during segments. A sequence is completely defined by a finite series of events and the intervals that separate them. By convention, every sequence begins with an event that marks the start of that sequence.

Figure 3: Synchronous Sampling

Synchronous and Asynchronous Systems: Consider a system with two periodic samplers with periods

T_1 and T_2 . If there exist positive integers N_1 and N_2 where $T_1 N_1 = T_2 N_2$, then the system is synchronous. For synchronous systems, the ratio of the sample periods is rational and the composite sample schedule is periodic (period = $T_1 N_1$). Conversely, if the ratio of sample periods is irrational then the composite event schedule is aperiodic and the system is asynchronous.

Synchronous Basic Time Period (BTP): The basic time period for synchronous systems is defined as $T_1 N_1$ where $T_1 N_1 = T_2 N_2$ and N_1 and N_2 have no common factors greater than unity.

Asynchronous BTP and Key Sequence: A basic time period can be selected for asynchronous systems. Select positive integers $\{N_1, N_2\}$ such that $T_1 N_1 \approx T_2 N_2$ and pick $k = 1$ or $k = 2$. Then, $T_k N_k$ is the BTP and the k 'th sample sequence is the key sequence (because the BTP is keyed to that sequence). There are infinite choices for the N 's. $T_1 N_1$ and $T_2 N_2$ can be arbitrarily close by choosing sufficiently large N 's (long BTP's).

Figure 4: Asynchronous Sampling

Phase: Phase is the elapsed time from the start of a BTP to the first discrete event in the "non-key" sequence. By convention, the BTP starts with the initial event in the key sequence. If $T_1 N_1 \neq T_2 N_2$, phase will be different in consecutive BTP's. If $\frac{T_1}{T_2}$ is irrational, then the system is asynchronous and phase is different in every BTP. In Figures 3 and 4, phase is indicated by τ . Note that, given T_1, T_2 , the BTP length, and τ for one BTP, phase (τ) is established for every other BTP.

Stability: Consider a linear system with a state vector $X(t)$ and a state transition matrix $\Psi(t_f, t_0)$ such that $X(t_f) = \Psi(t_f, t_0)X(t_0)$. A necessary and sufficient condition for global asymptotic stability is:

$$\lim_{t_f \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\sigma}(\Psi(t_f, t_0)) \rightarrow 0, \text{ for all } t_0 \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$ indicates the maximum singular value of a matrix. This means that every element in $\Psi(\infty, t_0)$ must go to zero.

Asynchronous Phase Distribution

Suppose $\frac{T_1}{T_2}$ is irrational and sequence 1 is the key sequence, then the phase over all future BTP's is uniformly distributed

on $[0, T_2]$. This assertion is offered without proof, but consider this example. Let $T_1 = 1$ and $T_2 = e$ where e is the base for natural logarithms. Suppose we choose $k = 1$ and $N_1 = 8$, so $BTP = 8$ and $N_2 = 3$. Figure 5 shows the resulting phase distribution for 162 consecutive BTP's. To use this Figure, draw

Figure 5: Asynchronous Phase Distribution Example

a horizontal line at n phase cycles; then, intersections with the vertical lines represent the phase values for 18n (approximately) consecutive BTP's. The first 18 BTP phase values are uniformly distributed on $[0, T_2]$. After eight more groups of 18 BTP's elapse, we see a denser, essentially uniform distribution over the same interval. As more BTP's are included, this general pattern repeats.

State Transition Matrix

The analysis method requires the calculation of the closed-loop (plant and the controller) state transition matrix for a BTP as a function of phase. Kalman and Bertram [3] described a systematic approach to construct this matrix. The essentials of this method are reviewed.

Figure 1 represents this general hybrid system. The state, which represents all the memory in the system, is partitioned into three parts:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ x_s \\ x_d \end{bmatrix}$$

where x_c is a column vector of continuous states (integrator outputs), x_s is a column vector of sample states, and x_d is a column vector of digital states. Sample and digital state transitions (S_i and D_i matrices) are basically the same. However, continuous state transitions only depend on the sample states and calculations are simplified by differentiating between x_s and x_d . Note that S_i and D_i must not create algebraic loops or the problem is ill-posed.

State Transitions: There are two types of state transitions: continuous-time transitions and discrete-time transitions. Continuous transitions occur during segments and discrete events occur between segments.

The continuous state transition can be computed for any time interval (Δt) containing no events. If the continuous state space description is $\dot{x}_c = Ax_c + Bu$ where $u(t) = x_s$, (x_s is constant during Δt) then from linear system theory [12] [13]:

$$X(t + \Delta t) = \begin{bmatrix} \phi(\Delta t) & \Gamma(\Delta t) & 0 \\ 0 & I_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_c(t) \\ x_s(t) \\ x_d(t) \end{bmatrix} \equiv \Phi(\Delta t)X(t) \quad (2)$$

where $\phi(\Delta t) = \exp(A\Delta t)$, $\Gamma(\Delta t) = \int_0^{\Delta t} \phi(x)Bdx$, and I_s and I_d are identity matrices of the appropriate size.

Sample and hold state transition matrices are found by inspection. For example, let $X \equiv [x_1 \dots x_n]^T$. Suppose that a sample event consists of sample and hold state "i" sampling state "p" through a gain K_p and state "q" through a gain K_q (i.e., $x_i(t^+) = K_p x_p(t^-) + K_q x_q(t^-)$). The corresponding state transition matrix is simply an identity matrix with the i 'th row replaced by:

$$[0 \dots 0 K_p 0 \dots 0 K_q 0 \dots 0]$$

where K_p is in the p 'th column and K_q is in the q 'th column.

Similarly, the digital state transition matrices are obtained directly from the difference equations by inserting the difference equation coefficients into the corresponding row of an identity matrix.

Constructing Ψ : Given the continuous system coefficients (A and B) and the event transition matrices (S_1, S_2, \dots and D_1, D_2, \dots), the state transition matrix for a BTP is easily constructed from the composite sequence of events. For example, if Figure 6 illustrates the events in a BTP, then the corresponding state transition matrix is simply:

$$\Psi = \Phi(t_2)D_2\Phi(t_1)D_1.$$

Figure 6: Event Timeline Illustration

Theory

First, consider the synchronous case. For the synchronous case, phase (τ) is the same for every BTP (recall Figure 3). Let $\Psi(\tau)$ be the state transition matrix for a synchronous BTP. Then a necessary and sufficient stability condition is simply $\bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau)) < 1$, where $\bar{\lambda}(\cdot)$ is the spectral radius (norm of largest eigenvalue) of a matrix.

The asynchronous stability condition is more complex. Using the same definitions for $\Psi(\tau)$ and $\bar{\lambda}(\cdot)$, let T be the period of the "non-key" sequence and let $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$ be the maximum singular value of a matrix. Then, a sufficient asynchronous stability condition is $\sigma^* < 0$ where:

$$\sigma^* \equiv \frac{1}{T} \frac{1}{BTP} \int_{\tau=0}^T (\log(\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))) + \log(\bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau)))) d\tau \quad (3)$$

and $\Delta(\tau)$ is defined by Equation 5 below. Now, $\Delta(\tau)$ is the safety factor to account for asynchronous sampling and that σ^* is like a rightmost bound on the poles of a linear time-invariant system.

Derivation

Factoring $\Psi(t_f, t_0)$: Divide $[t_f, t_0]$ into BTP's: n intervals, $[t_n, t_{n-1}], \dots, [t_2, t_1], [t_1, t_0]$ where of each $[t_i, t_{i-1}]$ is a BTP except for $[t_1, t_0]$ and $[t_n, t_{n-1}]$ which may be shorter. Then,

$n \rightarrow \infty$ as $t_f \rightarrow \infty$. Now, $\Psi(t_f, t_0)$ in Equation 1 can be factored as:

$$\Psi(t_f, t_0) = \Psi_n \Psi_{n-1} \cdots \Psi_2 \Psi_1 \quad (4)$$

where Ψ_i is defined as $\Psi(t_i, t_{i-1})$.

When the individual Ψ_i 's are diagonalizable (not defective) each Ψ_i can be factored ($\Psi_i = S_i \Lambda_i S_i^{-1}$) where Λ_i is a diagonal matrix of eigenvalues and S_i is a square matrix of eigenvectors. In general, both Λ_i and S_i are complex. Finally, factor each Λ_i as:

$$\Lambda_i = \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_i}{\bar{\lambda}_i}} \bar{\lambda}_i \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_i}{\bar{\lambda}_i}},$$

where $\bar{\lambda}_i \equiv \bar{\lambda}(\Psi_i)$ is the spectral radius of Ψ_i , a positive scalar. Substituting these into Equation 4 allows terms to be expanded as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_i \Psi_{i-1} &= S_i \Lambda_i S_i^{-1} S_{i-1} \Lambda_{i-1} S_{i-1}^{-1} \\ &= S_i \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_i}{\bar{\lambda}_i}} \bar{\lambda}_i \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_i}{\bar{\lambda}_i}} S_i^{-1} S_{i-1} \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_{i-1}}{\bar{\lambda}_{i-1}}} \bar{\lambda}_{i-1} \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_{i-1}}{\bar{\lambda}_{i-1}}} S_{i-1}^{-1} \\ &= S_i \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_i}{\bar{\lambda}_i}} \bar{\lambda}_i \Delta_i \bar{\lambda}_{i-1} \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_{i-1}}{\bar{\lambda}_{i-1}}} S_{i-1}^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where: $\Delta_i \equiv \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_i}{\bar{\lambda}_i}} S_i^{-1} S_{i-1} \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_{i-1}}{\bar{\lambda}_{i-1}}}$.

Note that $\bar{\lambda}_i$ is a positive scalar and Δ_i is a square complex matrix. Incidentally, the square root and the eigenvector matrix in Equation 5 are not unique. The choice of square root does not matter because either choice produces the same $\bar{\sigma}(\Delta_i)$. The choice of eigenvectors will be discussed later.

So, $\Psi(t_f, t_0)$ can be rewritten in factored form as:

$$\Psi(t_f, t_0) = S_n \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_n}{\bar{\lambda}_n}} \bar{\lambda}_n \Delta_n \bar{\lambda}_{n-1} \Delta_{n-1} \cdots \bar{\lambda}_2 \Delta_2 \bar{\lambda}_1 \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_1}{\bar{\lambda}_1}} S_1^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

General Stability Condition: Since $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$, the maximum singular value of a matrix, is a scalar, an equivalent form for Equation 1 is:

$$\lim_{t_f \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\sigma}(\Psi(t_f, t_0)) \rightarrow 0. \iff \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [\bar{\sigma}(\Psi_n \Psi_{n-1} \cdots \Psi_2 \Psi_1)]^{\frac{1}{n}} < 1.$$

Also, $\bar{\sigma}(YZ) \leq \bar{\sigma}(Y)\bar{\sigma}(Z)$. Applying this to Equation 6 gives:

$$\bar{\sigma}(\Psi_n \Psi_{n-1} \cdots \Psi_2 \Psi_1) \leq \bar{\sigma} \left(S_n \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_n}{\bar{\lambda}_n}} \bar{\lambda}_n \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_n) \bar{\lambda}_{n-1} \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_{n-1}) \cdots \bar{\lambda}_2 \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_2) \bar{\lambda}_1 \bar{\sigma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_1}{\bar{\lambda}_1}} S_1^{-1} \right) \right).$$

So a sufficient stability condition is:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left[\bar{\sigma} \left(S_n \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_n}{\bar{\lambda}_n}} \bar{\lambda}_n \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_n) \cdots \bar{\lambda}_2 \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_2) \bar{\lambda}_1 \bar{\sigma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_1}{\bar{\lambda}_1}} S_1^{-1} \right) \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}} < 1. \quad (7)$$

Let the Δ and $\bar{\lambda}$ terms in Equation 7 be grouped according to indexed classes with upper bounds σ_i and λ_j such that $\bar{\sigma}(\Delta) \leq \sigma_i$ for all the Δ 's in class "i" and $\bar{\lambda} \leq \lambda_j$ for all $\bar{\lambda}$'s in class "j". Also, for any interval, $[t_0, t_f]$, let n_{σ_i} be the number of Δ 's in class "i" and let n_{λ_j} be the number of $\bar{\lambda}$'s in class "j". Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\bar{\sigma} \left(S_n \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_n}{\bar{\lambda}_n}} \bar{\lambda}_n \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_n) \cdots \bar{\lambda}_2 \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_2) \bar{\lambda}_1 \bar{\sigma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_1}{\bar{\lambda}_1}} S_1^{-1} \right) \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}} &= \\ \left[\bar{\sigma} \left(S_n \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_n}{\bar{\lambda}_n}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \bar{\lambda}_k \right) \left(\prod_{k=2}^n \bar{\sigma}(\Delta_k) \right) \bar{\sigma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_1}{\bar{\lambda}_1}} S_1^{-1} \right) \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}} &\leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\left[\bar{\sigma} \left(S_n \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_n}{\bar{\lambda}_n}} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}} \prod_i \sigma_i^{\frac{n_{\sigma_i}}{n}} \prod_j \lambda_j^{\frac{n_{\lambda_j}}{n}} \left[\bar{\sigma} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_1}{\bar{\lambda}_1}} S_1^{-1} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}}.$$

Combine this with Equation 7 and note that in the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$, the first and last terms go to unity. The resulting sufficient stability condition is:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_i \sigma_i^{\frac{n_{\sigma_i}}{n}} \prod_j \lambda_j^{\frac{n_{\lambda_j}}{n}} = \prod_i \sigma_i^{p_{\sigma_i}} \prod_j \lambda_j^{p_{\lambda_j}} < 1 \quad (8)$$

where p_{σ_i} and p_{λ_j} are the probability of occurrence of state transition matrices with Δ in class i and $\bar{\lambda}$ in class j respectively. Finally, take the natural logarithm of Equation 8 to get:

$$\sum_i p_{\sigma_i} \log(\sigma_i) + \sum_j p_{\lambda_j} \log(\lambda_j) < 0, \quad (9)$$

an equivalent form of the sufficient stability condition.

Asynchronous Multirate Stability: Apply Equation 9 to the asynchronous multirate problem using phase regions to partition the Δ 's and λ 's into classes. Since phase is uniformly distributed, the probability of occurrence of a state transition matrix in the class defined by $\tau \in [t_1, t_2]$ is just $\frac{t_2 - t_1}{T}$ where T , as defined earlier, is the range of possible phase values (of course, $0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq T$).

Phase uniquely defines the BTP event timeline and also the timeline for previous BTP (consider Figure 4). Therefore, Ψ and Δ are functions of τ (i.e., $\Psi(\tau)$ and $\Delta(\tau)$).

After dividing the Δ 's and $\bar{\lambda}$'s into indexed classes using τ intervals of size $d\tau$, Equation 9 becomes:

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{d\tau}{T} \log(\sigma_i) \right) + \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \frac{d\tau}{T} \log(\lambda_j) \right) < 0 \quad (10)$$

where:

$$m \equiv \frac{T}{d\tau},$$

$$\lambda_j \equiv \sup(\bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau))), \tau \in [(j-1)d\tau, jd\tau], \text{ and}$$

$$\sigma_i \equiv \sup(\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))), \tau \in [(i-1)d\tau, id\tau].$$

In the limit as $d\tau \rightarrow 0$, the sums in Equation 10 become integrals:

$$\sigma^0 \equiv \frac{1}{T} \int_{\tau=0}^T \log(\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))) d\tau + \frac{1}{T} \int_{\tau=0}^T \log(\bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau))) d\tau < 0, \quad (11)$$

where Equation 11 defines the scalar σ^0 . Also, define $\sigma^* = \frac{\sigma^0}{BTF}$. The significance of σ^* will be discussed later.

Eigenvector Scaling

The eigenvector matrix (S), used to compute " Δ " in Equation 5, is not unique because eigenvector length is arbitrary. In fact, the choice of eigenvectors can change $\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))$, sometimes substantially. However, the best S (which minimizes $\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))$) is not obvious. Numerical stability is also a consideration. Numerical properties are improved by choosing S in a balanced form such that the norms of the columns of S are the same as the norms of the corresponding rows of S^{-1} . This balanced form improves the condition number of S significantly and usually is less conservative than choosing unit eigenvectors.

Analysis

Before discussing an example, consider the significance of Equation 11. Comparing this with Equations 6 and 7 one can conclude that, in some average fashion, $\log(\bar{\sigma}(\Psi(t+BTP, t))) \leq \sigma^0$. Therefore, if X_0 is some initial error state and X_1 is the state one BTP later, on the average, $\|X_1\| \leq \|X_0\| \exp(\sigma^0)$. Hence, σ^0 represents a maximum (conservative bound) decay constant for one BTP. To be more precise, if the initial state error is $X(0)$, then the residual error $\|X(t)\|$ will be less than $\|X(0)\| \exp(\sigma^* t)$ for most values of $t \in [0, \infty)$. So, σ^* is an average, conservative decay constant per unit time.

Now consider the integrands of Equation 11. The BTP state transition matrix is an analytic function of phase except at a finite number of points [11]. Hence, the $\bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau))$'s and $\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))$'s are continuous functions of τ except at a few known values so the integrals can be computed numerically without great difficulty.

Plots of the integrands of Equation 11 versus τ give substantial insight into the system behavior since they show how stability varies with phase. For a synchronous system, $\log \bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau))$ must be negative for the actual phase for the system to be stable. For asynchronous systems, a plot of $\log \bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))$ versus τ shows the potential destabilizing effect of asynchronous sampling.

One should not equate large negative values of σ^* with good performance. For example, lightly damped estimator modes can be perfectly acceptable when measurement noise is small. Increasing the damping for some state errors may reduce damping of more critical errors. Therefore, σ^* should only be used to assess stability, not performance.

The next section illustrates these stability concepts with a simple example. Notational abbreviations $\lambda(\tau) \equiv \bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau))$ and $\sigma(\tau) \equiv \bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))$ are used for a compact notation that emphasizes the functional dependence of $\lambda(\cdot)$ and $\sigma(\cdot)$ on τ .

Example

This simple example illustrates some the unusual behavior possible in asynchronous systems. The system is a double integrator plant with digital position feedback and a crude digital rate feedback (See Figure 7). The position and rate feedback represent two coupled but independent and possibly asynchronous sample processes. With analog state feedback, such a system is stable for all positive gains. With sampled position and rate feedback, the system is stable only with high rate feedback. The asynchronous digital system is fourth order and more interesting.

Position feedback sampling is the key sequence. For the synchronous case, the sample periods are $T_1=T_2=1.0$ and for the "asynchronous" case, $T_1=1$ and $T_2=0.9$. The basic time period (BTP) for both cases is 1.0. This so-called asynchronous case is clearly synchronous with a BTP of 9.0; however, this fiction allows direct comparison of the asynchronous result with an exact synchronous analysis.

This idea of using asynchronous analysis techniques and a short BTP for a synchronous system has valid uses. For example, suppose some system were synchronous with BTP=100 but we are interested in the response during a much shorter time (say 1). Then it would be useful to analyze the system with a small "asynchronous" BTP (near 1) to understand the short-term stability of the system. Furthermore, calculations are easier with shorter BTP's.

Figure 7: Block Diagram for Example System

Nominal Case

At the nominal condition, both samplers operate at one sample per second. Figure 8 shows the stability condition (Equation 11) integrands versus phase for synchronous sampling. The $\sigma(\tau)$ term is unity for any synchronous case because

Figure 8: Synchronous Stability Plot, Nominal Gains

$S_i = S_{i-1}$ (Equation 5) so $\log(\bar{\sigma}(\Delta))=0$ for all phase values. The $\lambda(\tau)$ term varies with phase. The system is stable when phase is greater than 0.28 and unstable for phase less than 0.28. Therefore, the stability depends on the phase relationships between the two samplers. This is easy to understand from Figure 7. When the rate sampler operates just after the position sampler, the effective rate feedback gain is nearly zero. As the rate sampler delay (phase) increases, the effective rate feedback gain increases and so does the stability, until the delay exceeds a quarter of the natural period where the effective rate feedback gain starts to decrease.

If Figure 8 actually represented an asynchronous system, that asynchronous system would be stable overall ($\sigma^* = -0.06$) but state errors would grow during some BTP's. Such behavior may be acceptable if "unstable" BTP's are mixed with stable BTP's. Conversely, if there are many consecutive "unstable" BTP's, the behavior may be unacceptable.

Asynchronous Case

Consider the case where the rate sampler is slightly faster with a period of 0.9. Analyzing this configuration using the same BTP (1.0) gives $\sigma^* = -0.031$ and the curves in Figure 9. The stability contribution of $\bar{\lambda}(\Psi(\tau))$ overcomes the possible destabilizing effect of $\bar{\sigma}(\Delta(\tau))$ (the BTP mismatch). Since the sam-

Figure 9: Asynchronous Stability Plot, Nominal Gains

pling is actually synchronous, phase (τ) is not uniformly distributed; rather, it cycles through a sequence of specific values (say 1.0, 0.9, 0.8, ... 0.2, 0.1) producing a discrete uniform distribution. Conceivably, actual values of $\log \lambda(\tau)$ and $\log \sigma(\tau)$ could be averaged for actual phase values if the exact phasing is known. However, σ^* is still a good indicator for the synchronous case with known or random phase, providing the analysis BTP is much shorter than the true BTP.

As noted earlier, this so-called asynchronous example is synchronous with BTP=9.0. We use this fact to determine the exact stability. Figure 10 shows stability integrands computed

Figure 10: Stability Plot, Nominal Gains, True BTP

for the true, synchronous BTP (BTP=9). Comparing with the previous plot, we see the sufficient condition was conservative since the "worst" $\log(\lambda)$ is about -0.08 compared with the asynchronous $\sigma^* = -0.031$ result. Even so, the asynchronous plot shows that state errors grow during BTP=1 intervals with $0.1 \leq \tau \leq 0.2$. In practice, BTP's can be selected to get a "sharp" result.

Conclusion

A sufficient asynchronous stability condition was developed. The resulting figure of merit describes a conservative exponential envelope which bounds the average error state decay for any initial state error condition. The figure of merit is found through numerical integration of quantities computed from the system state transition matrix. The integrands also provide physical insight into system behavior.

The method is applicable to multi-input/multi-output, linear hybrid systems whenever the basic time period (BTP) state transition matrix has a full set of eigenvectors for the non-zero eigenvalues.

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